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Preliminary analysis and selection of the zeolite materials to be tested

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

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Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION	6
2	MATERIALS AND METHODS	6
2.1	Adsorbent materials	6
2.2	Preparation and characterization of synthetic materials	7
2.3	TGA-DTA furnace	12
2.4	LAB-SCALE SETUP FOR ADSORPTION TESTS	13
3	MAIN RESULTS	14
4	CONCLUSIONS	19

1 INTRODUCTION

WP4 activities aim at further strengthening the reduction of carbon footprint along the entire cement and concrete value chain. One of the goals of the WP4 is to use captured CO₂-rich streams in a zeolite-based CO₂ mineralization plant based on the BUZZI patented technology (Italian Patent 10202000024427, Oct.2020) integrated with the Vernasca cement plant operated by BUZZI for the production of CO₂-trapped natural and synthetic zeolites. CO₂-enriched materials will then be used as Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) for casting concrete with lower cement content and lower carbon footprint. According to this technology, during cement hydration, part of the CO₂ entrapped in zeolites will be released enabling the precipitation of nanocrystalline seed of CaCO₃, promoting the cement hydration and storing part of the CO₂ for the whole lifecycle of the building material.

The aim of this report is to give an overview of the preliminary activities carried out in Task T4.2 (Engineering, construction and demonstration of the zeolites-based mineralization plant) to screen the potential zeolites candidates for the CO₂ capture in the mineralization plant; in particular, different adsorbents were tested, through preliminary lab-scale experiments, to assess the CO₂ uptake capacity under different conditions. Several zeolites, both natural and synthetic, and other common materials were considered; their adsorption performances were compared with those of a reference commercial product, the synthetic 13X zeolite.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Adsorbent materials

Several common materials, both natural and synthetic, provided by the partners involved in the WP4 activities, were tested (Table 1).

Biochar CPK1 (20% water) and Biochar CPK5 (5% water) are carbonaceous materials obtained by thermal degradation. Due to their significant fraction of macropores, they are characterized by different percentages of humidity and appear as black crumbly flakes of very light weight.

Icelandic pozzolana is a pyroclastic volcanic slag composed of siliceous and aluminous material. It appears as a really fine ash that, in combination with water and calcium hydroxide, can generate a hydraulic material.

Zeolite from Mexico, Zeolite from Slovenia (Montana), Zeolite from Slovakia, and Zeolite from Ukraine are natural zeolites coming from different areas of the world that have been provided in the form of small rocks (mm and cm size) or as powders.

Raw material (ASH 1) and Raw material (ASH 2) are two primary raw materials that have been functionalized by ARTIDEK as Z1 (Artidek 1) and Z2 (Artidek 2) in order to increase their capability of adsorption, following the procedure described in the following section. Other synthetic zeolites, samples from Z3 to Z9N1 have been also synthesized with the same experimental procedure.

Unburnt coal is a compound rich in carbon that originates from the exhaust gases of a coal combustion station. It has been inserted in the study due to its promising potential as adsorbent material in the retention of various pollutants from both liquid and gaseous environments.

Table 1: List of the analyzed materials.

Solid adsorbent
Zeolite Slovakia
Zeolite Ukraine
Zeolite Mexico
Zeolite Slovenia
Pozzolana Iceland
Biochar CPK5 5% water
Biochar CPK1 20% water
Ash 1
Ash 2
Unburnt coal
Z1 (Artidek 1)
Z2 (Artidek 2)
Z3
Z4
Z5
Z6
Z9M
Z9(2)
Z9 N1
Zeolite 13x (commercial material)

In addition to the materials listed in Table 1, Zeolite 13X was also considered. Zeolite 13X is a well-known material, commonly used as molecular sieve in many industrial applications due to its high adsorption capacity, particularly CO₂ and water, which makes this adsorbent the best candidate as reference material for the comparison of the adsorption and desorption capacities of the materials selected in this project. It is typically available in a pelletized form, exhibiting a uniform and high level of porosity that characterizes its strong and selective adsorption capacity.

2.2 Preparation and characterization of synthetic materials

Different literature studies highlighted that it is possible to modify and control the adsorption activity and selectivity of zeolites regulating their pore diameter by means of a cationic exchange process [1-5].

However, the effect of cationic exchange might be positive or negative, depending on the zeolites type and on gaseous specie to be adsorbed. Considering the goal to adsorb selectively CO₂, it was found that Zeolite X, Zeolite Y, Zeolite A, and chabazite typically show high potential to be rather investigated for the aims of task T4.2. In addition, the Na- modification of zeolites shows high stability of the adsorption capacity under alternating adsorption-desorption steps. Therefore, it is reasonable to use Na- forms of zeolites as a solid sorbent in the post-combustion system for the CO₂ capture.

Moreover, the Na-forms of zeolites needs a relatively short series of simple steps to be produced. Also, the amount of waste that is generated and, therefore, had to be reprocessed, is less for the production of Na-form of zeolites. For this reason, Na-form of zeolites X, Y, LTA were selected as target products for the further synthesis and the experimental investigation.

For the preparation of synthetic zeolites, cheap materials rich in silica and alumina were selected. For this reason, coal fly ashes from thermal power plants were used; they are abundant wastes with low (even up to negative) cost that contains silica and alumina in active forms. There are also some references in the literature about possible processes for the chemical modification of fly ashes [6-14]. After a preliminary selection, a two-steps hydrothermal process was defined. This process allows modifying alumina-silica raw materials in which the silica/alumina rate is higher than desired (as it usually takes place for the main alumina-silicate substances, for example, for coal ashes). Fly ashes were digested with a strong alkali solution (the concentration of NaOH is between 2M and 4M) under mild conditions (about 50°C in an open vessel) for a period of 2-4 days, depending on the specific material used. Under such conditions, the nuclei of the crystallites having crystal framework that is desirable may be obtained via accurate adjustment of the digesting parameters (pH, temperature, solid/liquid rate). All exceeded silica is dissolved in the form of sodium silicate during that stage. When digesting is completed (must be controlled experimentally), the temperature of the mixture is increased to 75-90°C to provide the growth of the crystal of zeolites from the nuclei. Several processes taking place simultaneously during this stage:

- 1- Growth of the crystals of target zeolite (for example, NaX). It is the only useful and desirable process;
- 2- Re-crystallization of the target zeolite to more stable ones (NaP1, hydro-sodalite, analcime). These processes are harmful and undesirable.

To avoid the undesirable processes, the temperature and the process duration are controlled accurately.

After the target zeolite crystals were grown, they were separated from the supernatant, washed with distilled water to lower the pH below 10 and dried at 80-90°C to obtain "raw zeolite", and then calcined at 350-450°C to obtain the thermal activated form. The thermal activation cannot be longer than 4 hours and at temperature below 450°C to avoid a possible reduction of the CO₂ adsorption capacity.

Washing water may be used to further compensate the water evaporation during the digesting and crystallization processes. Materials obtained after this first step can be used for the CO₂ capture and the remaining liquid of the process, the supernatant, can undergo a second series of treatments to obtain other solids able to adsorb CO₂.

In a second step the supernatant is treated with a sodium aluminate solution (obtained using the external alumina source). The amount of added aluminate is calculated preliminary to get Si/Al molar ratio in the reaction mixture in the range 0.8-1.2. After mixing and stirring for several hours at room temperature, the initially transparent liquor becomes milky, then snow-white precipitate is sedimented. Two main processes occur in this phase:

- 1 - Sodium silicate that was obtained from sodium hydroxide and exceeding ashes silica interacts with the sodium aluminate with generation of insoluble amorphous sodium alumina-silicate and regenerated sodium hydroxide (solid "regeneration");
- 2 - Amorphous sodium alumina-silicate changes structure with the generation of the nuclei of crystallites with the zeolite framework (named "permutite"). The temperature, pH, the stirring intensity have a relevant influence on this step.

When the precipitate is formed, and solution becomes transparent again, the temperature of the mix is increased again to 75-90°C and kept in this range for about 2-3 days to provide the crystals' growth. After that, the zeolites crystals are separated from the supernatant; then are washed, dried, and calcined as it was described above.

The supernatant can be reused for a new synthesis. It is eventually necessary to adjust the volume and the pH of the solution to the initial amounts via adding the NaOH solution. The NaOH addition is needed to compensate that amount of NaOH that was integrated into the zeolite framework during the generation process.

A flow-chart of the two-steps process is reported in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Sketch of the two-steps process adopted for the preparation of synthetic zeolites.

Several synthetic zeolite samples were prepared, optimizing progressively the operating conditions of the process; their chemical composition was characterized by means of X-ray fluorescence (Expert 4L analyzer) and the framework structure of crystals was determined using the X-ray diffractometer Bruker D8 Advance. As raw materials were mainly used Coal ash from the Darnytsa TPP (Thermal Power Plant), Coal ash from the Ladizhyn TPP, Incinerator bottom ash and "White slag", both provided by Buzzi.

Samples Z1 and Z2 were generated during the first step, starting from the two different ashes got from the TPPs. All the ashes were preliminary decarbonized via flotation and separated from magnetic particles. The Z1 sample was prepared from the ash obtained as a by-product of the combustion of anthracite coal on the Darnytsa TPP, while the Z2 sample was prepared from the ash obtained as a by-product of the combustion of the "long-flame" coal on the Ladizhyn TPP. The chemical composition of initial ashes and the samples Z1 and Z2 are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Chemical composition of initial ashes and the samples Z1 and Z2 (w/w%).

Oxides	Ash from Dartytsa TPP	Sample Z1	Ash from Ladizhyn TPP	Sample Z2
MgO	1.58	1.96	3.58	2.22
Al ₂ O ₃	17.02	20.71	18.01	17.37
SiO ₂	50.36	44.33	56.62	45.99
P ₂ O ₅	1.06	0.46	0.49	0.19
SO ₃	0.43	0.09	0.33	0.07
K ₂ O	4.21	1.57	3.97	1.28
CaO	7.34	7.97	4.95	4.83
TiO ₂	1.77	2.29	1.15	2.70
V ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.03
MnO ₂	0.34	0.37	0.11	0.22
Fe ₂ O ₃	15.23	19.69	10.58	24.81
Ni ₂ O ₃	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.07
CuO	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03
ZnO	0.05	0.06	0.02	0.06
SrO	0.19	0.17	0.04	0.05
Y ₂ O ₃	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
ZrO ₂	0.16	0.11	0.05	0.05
BaO	0.13	0.08	0.03	0.02

As an example, the XRD patterns of the sample Z1 is reported in Fig. 2. The XRD patterns highlighted that Z1 sample contains mainly peaks of NaX zeolite, with the intensity of the main peak equal to 600 units. On the other hand, the Z2 sample contains peaks of both NaP and NaX zeolites, and the intensity of the main peak is less than 450. Therefore, the Z2 sample contains a lower amount of useful zeolite NaX than the Z1 sample, but it contains also NaP zeolite that can reduce the capacity to adsorb CO₂.

Fig. 2: XRD pattern of the sample Z1 (blue) superposed to the one of 100% NaX zeolites etalon (black).

Based on the results of the previous tests, the ash from the Darnytsa TPP was used for the preparation of other samples. Z3 sample was generated with a modified experimental setup (the reactor was enlarged to increase the production per each cycle). Other parameters were the same of the Z1 synthesis. The influence of some additives was investigated during the preparation of samples Z4 and Z5; for the Z4 synthesis, sodium aluminate was added to the mix before the digestion stage to bond excess silica "in situ", while for Z5 sodium aluminate was added to the supernatant after the treated ash was separated (i.e. after the digestion and crystallization stages) as prescribed in the second step of the previously described method. A comparison of the XRD patterns of these samples is reported in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Comparison among the XRD patterns of samples Z1, Z3, Z4, and Z5.

The crystalline phase for samples Z1 and Z3 is the same – zeolite NaX. However, the peaks intensity for the Z3 sample is 1.3-1.5 times higher than for the Z1 sample. It means that Z3 sample contain larger value of zeolite NaX. On the other hand, the Z4 sample contain some additional crystalline phases, apart NaX zeolite. Moreover, the NaX peaks intensity for the Z4 sample is very low, being this zeolite is just a minor component of the Z4 sample; the main crystal phases are those of NaP zeolite and LTA zeolite with the equal concentrations. Therefore, it seems that the use of an additional alumina source before the ash is digested is not useful to improve the quality of the final material.

The Z5 sample excels among the others. Intensity of the NaX peaks on its XRD pattern is the largest among all the samples. Additionally, it contains LTA zeolite with good concentration, and this should ensure a good CO₂ adsorption capacity for this sample.

Considering the necessity to produce more zeolites for the future experimental campaigns, a new synthesis setup with a reactor of 5 liters was then realized. Z6 sample was produced with the new setup, based on methodology used for the Z3 sample. The Z9 samples were obtained on the second step of the process. However, to reduce the amount of LTA zeolite in the product, the amount of sodium aluminate we added in lower amounts. In this case, there was no precipitation of the solid at room temperature even after overnight stirring the mix. Just after heating to 80°C the crystals start to growth on the glass surface of the reactor (not in the bulk, as it was earlier). The first relatively big crystals collected were marked Z9M. After that, the temperature was increased to 90°C and a second sample was picked (marked Z9-1). A third sample (marked Z9-2) was finally obtained after 7 days.

XRD analysis confirmed that the Z6 sample contains the same crystal phase (zeolite NaX), and in equal amounts, of the Z3 sample, thus confirming the successful scale-up of the process. The Z-9M sample contains two main crystalline phases: zeolites NaX and LTA, as the Z5 sample does. But the content of NaX zeolite in the Z-9M sample is lower than in the Z-5 sample. At the same time, the content of LTA zeolite is higher in the Z-9m sample than in the Z5 one. In general, the difference in the NaX/LTA ratio between the Z9M and Z5 samples should not influence significantly the adsorption capacity of the solid. On the other hand, the main crystalline phase for the Z-9-1 sample is LTA zeolite; as reported in the above mentioned literature, zeolite type A in the NA form could worsen the CO₂ adsorption capacity, than NaX.

2.3 TGA-DTA furnace

The Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was the main experimental technique used during this activity to evaluate the adsorption and desorption capacities of the investigated material at various conditions; TGA analyses were carried on with the TA Instruments SDT Q600, which provides simultaneous measurement of weight change (TGA) and true differential temperature (DTA) on the same sample (Fig. 4).

The primary parameter whose impact on the materials was analyzed is the purge flow of CO₂, and specifically how each material is able to adsorb and release it over time under different conditions in terms of temperature, gas flow-rate, and composition of the CO₂-containing stream.

Fig. 4: TGA-DTA furnace used for experimental tests.

The operating conditions of the adsorption/desorption method were adjusted according to the goals of the tests and taking into account also the properties of the materials; despite these small differences, the experimental procedure was always constituted by three main steps (Fig. 5):

- Conditioning phase (in a nitrogen or air atmosphere), intended to remove the residual humidity of the sample and to prepare the equilibrium (iso-thermal) conditions at which the adsorption and desorption phases have to be performed;
- Adsorption phase (in a CO₂-rich atmosphere), which allows for determining the maximum CO₂ adsorption of the sample at prescribed temperature and CO₂ concentration of the gas stream;
- Desorption phase, where there is the progressive release of the adsorbed CO₂.

Fig. 5: Typical TG profiles obtained in adsorption/desorption tests (Conditioning phase: blue; Adsorption: green; Desorption: yellow).

Results of TG tests were useful to select a reduced number of natural and synthetic zeolites that showed good CO₂ capture capacity and were considered promising for the use in the CO₂ mineralization pilot plant.

2.4 LAB-SCALE SETUP FOR ADSORPTION TESTS

A series of experimental tests was carried out with some of the materials selected from TG tests in a lab-scale equipment that allows for testing adsorbents in a configuration that is similar to those that can be found in both pilot and real-scale adsorption plants. For lab-scale tests, up to 100 g of each sample, were packed in a fixed-bed column and the adsorbent was flushed with a CO₂-rich gas stream at room temperature and atmospheric pressure, so as to reproduce the typical operating conditions of the gas stream that will be available for the CO₂ mineralization pilot plant. A sketch of the experimental setup for adsorption tests is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Experimental setup used for adsorption tests with CO₂-rich streams.

A couple of mass flow controllers (MFC) were used to regulate the gas flow-rate and the feed stream composition, thus allowing to perform experiments with a CO₂ concentration in the range 10-100 v/v%; the residual CO₂ concentration at the outlet of the column was recorded by an online gas

analyzer Horiba PG-250. Thermocouples and a pressure transducer were also used to monitor heat transfer effects (i.e. heat release during the adsorption) and the operating pressure during the test.

3 MAIN RESULTS

As previously mentioned, the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) technique was used to evaluate the adsorption and desorption capacities of the investigated materials; in particular it was possible to assess the maximum CO₂ adsorbed at constant temperature and equilibrium conditions as well as the adsorption/desorption dynamics. A typical experimental curve obtained from TG tests is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Experimental trends recorded in a TG test performed with sample Z1; the sample mass (green curve) can change as a function of both the temperature (blue curve) and the gas composition.

With reference to Fig. 7, it is possible to notice that physically adsorbed volatiles (mainly water) are released during the first 90 min, about 19% of initial mass, as expected during the conditioning phase. Then, once the temperature is stabilized at 30°C, a slight mass increase, due to the nitrogen adsorption, is initially observed before to switch the feed composition from nitrogen to 100% CO₂. The CO₂ loading by adsorption (120-180 min) is about 9.7 w/w% of the sample mass (1.98 mg). Then, switching again the feed stream from CO₂ to nitrogen, the desorption curve is recorded. CO₂ desorption at 30°C (180-300 min) is not complete (about 80% of the adsorbed amount is released) and the complete adsorbent regeneration is reached only after the final heating up to 600°C.

These tests were carried out with all the investigated adsorbents so as to assess the maximum CO₂ adsorption capacity at 30°C, atmospheric pressure, and with an atmosphere of 100% CO₂. As the material could be heterogeneous, a series of repeatability tests were also performed and a maximum deviation of ± 0.5 w/w% from the average CO₂ load was recorded for all the samples, apart from Z6 which showed a ± 1.2 w/w% deviation from the average load. Maximum amounts of adsorbed CO₂ are summarized in Table 3. For some samples, similar tests were carried out with different gas compositions (10 and 20 v/v% of CO₂, respectively) to evaluate the adsorption capacity of the material when it is exposed to gas mixtures with a composition that can be typically found in exhaust gas streams from cement plants. This way, it was possible to obtain the so-called CO₂ adsorption isotherms for the selected samples, as reported in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Experimental CO₂ adsorption isotherms obtained for some of the investigated adsorbents.

Table 3: Maximum CO₂ load for the investigated dry solids at 30°C and with a 100% CO₂ atmosphere.

Solid adsorbent (dry)	w/w% CO ₂
Zeolite Slovakia	3.3
Zeolite Ukraine	3.9
Zeolite Mexico	3.7
Zeolite Slovenia	3.6
Pozzolana Iceland	0.1
Biochar CPK5 5% water	5.0
Biochar CPK1 20% water	4.9
Ash 1	0.14
Ash 2	0.06
Unburnt coal	0.28
Z1 (Artidek 1)	10.7
Z2 (Artidek 2)	8.2
Z3	14.2
Z4	7.3
Z5	21.4
Z6	10.5
Z9M	18.3
Z9(2)	12.2
Z9 N1	15.1
Zeolite 13x (commercial material)	18.7

Apart from the reference commercial material, Zeolite 13X, the adsorption isotherms of the other materials clearly show that good CO₂ capture performances can be obtained also with gas streams with a CO₂ content of 10-20 v/v%, reaching at least 80% of the maximum CO₂ load that can be reached with a 100% CO₂ stream.

In addition, it was verified that the capacity to capture CO₂ of the investigated materials can be reasonably related to surface area and porosity of the solid particles, as confirmed by the results shown in Fig. 9, where the maximum CO₂ loading is reported as a function of the surface area (measured by means of BET techniques) for several samples.

Fig. 9: Maximum CO₂ load vs BET surface area for some of the investigated adsorbents.

It is also worth noticing that the two-step process used to prepare the synthetic zeolites was strongly enhancing the capacity of the materials to capture CO₂, as can be seen from the results of Table 3: raw materials collected from the TPPs exhibit a maximum CO₂ load of about 0.1 w/w%, while the corresponding synthetic zeolites, Z1 and Z2, were able to load about 10.7 and 8.2 w/w% of CO₂, thus reaching adsorption capacity that is 2-3 times higher than the CO₂ load obtained with natural zeolites (i.e., zeolites from Ukraine, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Mexico). The good results obtained with the synthetic zeolites were consistent with the results of the characterizations of the same materials carried out by XRD (X-ray Diffraction) and SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope). As shown in Fig. 10 for two specific materials, the Z2 sample and the corresponding raw material, Ash 2, the strong impact of the two-step process of preparation of synthetic zeolites on the morphology and structure of the solid particles is clearly visible, resulting in increased porosity (confirmed also by BET analyses) and crystallinity of the treated materials.

Fig. 10: SEM images: (left) raw Ash 2 (BET=6.2 m²/g) and (right) Z2 sample (BET=188 m²/g).

Among the adsorbent materials that exhibited the best performances to capture CO₂, some were also tested in the lab-scale apparatus. When necessary natural zeolites were ground and sieved to select

solids with a particle size fraction that can be easily managed in a packed column; particles with relatively large size (average diameter of about 1 mm) and quite broad particle size distribution are easy to load/unload in a fixed bed column, pressure drop are low, and fine dust particles are non entrained in the flow of the CO₂-rich stream, thus avoiding possible issues for the experimental setup. For this reason, lab-scale tests involved only natural zeolites and biochar; in fact, synthetic zeolites are characterized by very fine particles (average size: 20-30 μm), too fine for their direct use in a real-scale plant. Accordingly, a process to agglomerate such small particles into granules or pellets with more suitable size is under investigation to ensure the possibility to load these materials inside the mineralization pilot plant without safety issues for workers and acceptable pressure drop inside the equipment.

Initially, the experimental tests performed with the lab-scale equipment were used to confirm and validate the results obtained with the TG analyzer. Then, further experiments were run at different values of specific operating parameters, such as the gas velocity inside the bed and the humidity content of the adsorbent, to gain information useful to define reference conditions for the design and the operation of the pilot plant. With this experimental setup, the adsorbent bed is fed with a gas stream at constant flow-rate and constant concentration of CO₂. The corresponding CO₂ loading of the investigated material is then derived by monitoring the CO₂ concentration at the outlet of the column and combining this information with a simple material balance. As shown in the example of Fig. 11, this kind of experiments allows for obtaining the so-called breakthrough curve; this curve is the time-resolved effluent CO₂ concentration of the adsorbent under investigation. Adsorption capacity and selectivity, release and transfer of heat as well as the adsorption rate, inlet concentration and gas velocity all determine the dynamic adsorption process, fully reflected by position and shape of the breakthrough curve. The adsorption capacity is primarily related to the area below the breakthrough curve: increasing the adsorption capacity, the breakthrough curve will be shifted to longer breakthrough times (to the right), because more gas species will be retained by the adsorbent. On the other hand, the adsorption kinetics affects the shape of the breakthrough curve: at decreasing mass transport resistances, the breakthrough curve becomes steeper (sharper) and the mass transfer zone smaller. A fast mass transfer from the gas phase to the adsorption sites leads to short local equilibration times and, therefore, it results in steeper concentration front.

As evidenced by the curves of Fig. 11, obtained packing the column with different solid samples, the CO₂ concentration (normalized with respect to the CO₂ concentration of the inlet stream) at the outlet of the column rapidly increases after 1-2 minutes; this means that the CO₂ adsorption is very fast and the adsorbent reaches its maximum CO₂ load in a few minutes when exposed to a CO₂-rich stream.

Fig. 11: Example of breakthrough curve obtained for different investigated samples at room temperature (dry adsorbents).

Breakthrough experiments helped also to evaluate the possible interference of water vapor (or moisture of the solid) on the CO₂ adsorption capacity, as well as to highlight the influence of the gas

velocity on both adsorption and desorption dynamics, as reported in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13, respectively. About the effect of moisture or water vapor, several experiments were carried out and all the tests evidenced an expected high competitive adsorption of water that basically reduce of about 40-50% the solid capacity to adsorb CO₂. For this reason, a thermal pre-treatment of the adsorbent to reduce its moisture content has to be implemented for the effective operation of the mineralization pilot plant. For the same reason, it will be also important to perform a dehumidification treatment of the CO₂-containing stream if the water content of the feed stream will be too high.

Fig. 12: Effect of moisture in the sample or humidity in the feed stream for the Zeolite Slovenia sample (left) and comparison of different breakthrough trends obtained for solids that were exposed to the CO₂-rich stream without performing their drying pre-treatment (right).

Fig. 13: Effect of the gas velocity on the CO₂ adsorption (feed: air with 10% of CO₂) and desorption (feed: air) dynamics on the Zeolite Slovakia sample.

As shown in Figure 13, loading and unloading behaviors are affected by the gas velocity at limited extent: this means that this parameter can be tuned in order to find the best compromise between the process time and the pressure drop.

On the other hand, while fast loading is definitely welcome, too fast desorption kinetics could be negative when looking at the final use of the loaded materials, that is their role of CO₂ supplier to the cementitious formulation. To elucidate these aspects, additional tests were run using solids previously loaded by CO₂ and left inside the column open to the atmosphere: starting from an initial CO₂ loading of 3-4 w/w%, about 20-25% of the CO₂ was desorbed in the first 24 hours, and 35-40% in 5 days. This means that solids loaded inside a bed in a few minutes, taking advantage of the effective gas-solid contact typical of these units, can desorb much more slowly provided that the gas contact is poor enough, a promising behavior in view of the CO₂ release after mixing with the other components of the cementitious mixture.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The activities of this task were focused on screening potential zeolite candidates for CO₂ capture to be then used in the cement industry. Various adsorbent materials, both natural and synthetic, were tested for their CO₂ uptake capacity under different conditions.

A diverse range of materials were tested, including different types of natural zeolites (from Slovakia, Ukraine, Mexico, and Slovenia), Icelandic pozzolana, biochar (with different water contents), raw and functionalized ashes, unburnt coal, and various synthetic zeolites. The reference commercial product used for comparison was synthetic 13X zeolite.

Synthetic zeolites were prepared using a two-step hydrothermal process involving mainly coal fly ashes from thermal power plants. This process enhanced the capacity of the materials to capture CO₂ by increasing their porosity and crystallinity. The preparation process involved specific conditions of temperature and the addition of sodium aluminate to optimize the formation of NaX and LTA zeolites. Many experimental tests, performed with a TGA equipment, allowed to study preliminarily the adsorption dynamics of CO₂ and to assess the maximum CO₂ load of all the investigated sorbents; natural zeolites showed a 3-4 w/w% CO₂ load capacity, while several synthetic zeolites showed higher CO₂ adsorption capacities compared to natural zeolites, with a load of CO₂ often above 10 w/w%.

Lab-scale experiments were also conducted to test the adsorption capacities of selected materials. These tests involved a packed-bed column setup where adsorbents were exposed to CO₂-rich streams, and breakthrough curves were used to assess the adsorption performance.

The adsorption and desorption capacities of the materials are influenced by factors such as gas velocity, humidity, and the concentration of the CO₂ in the gas stream. Moisture content was found to significantly reduce the CO₂ adsorption capacity (about 40-50%) of the materials.

Natural zeolites were successfully used in the lab-scale equipment, giving also useful information for the design of the mineralization pilot plant and for the definition of operating conditions for the pilot tests. About synthetic zeolites, despite their promising performances, the actual particle size does not allow a direct use in the lab-scale equipment or in the pilot plant, so it will be investigated a granulation or pelletization process to increase the particles size and to avoid possible practical issues during the mineralization tests.

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